
EXPERT FEEDBACK ON TOURISM AND FISHERIES IN THE ARCTIC

Expert feedback on tourism in the Arctic

LITTLE AUK

Isfjorden

Population

↘ 20K

Highlights

Hornsund and NW Svalbard populations are stable

Challenges

Active breeding population in decline

Tourism

Impact at sea: medium
Impact on land: medium
Value: medium

Top 3 influences
Sea Ice
Seawater Temperature
Nutrients

Distribution of (fish) species is evolving, which is impacting the whole ecosystem and will affect livelihoods; evolving climate conditions that might affect both positively and negatively some human activities (e.g. ship traffic, activities dependent on snow/ice).

PUFFIN

Isfjorden

Population

↗ 5K

Highlights

Increasing due to climate change

Challenges

May draw tourist ships into new areas

Tourism

Impact at sea: medium
Impact on land: medium
Value: high

Top 3 influences
Seawater Temperature
Sea Ice
Light

There are many opportunities for the tourism sector and host communities: longer opportunities seasons, greater access to areas previously inaccessible.

WALRUS

Isfjorden

Population

↗ 6K

Highlights

Slowly recovering following protection scheme (70's)

Challenges

Females with calves are still a rare sight

Tourism

Impact at sea: low
Impact on land: low
Value: high

Top 3 influences
Nutrients
Sea Ice
Seawater Temperature

Increased risks, especially in terms of natural hazards, but also in balancing environmental degradation with increased tourism volume and the pressure that creates on the environment, on infrastructure and on community well-being.

WHALES

Isfjorden

Population

Highlights

Sightings are becoming increasingly common

Challenges

Populations increase only due to enforced protection

Tourism

Impact at sea: medium
Impact on land: low
Value: high

Top 3 influences

Sea Ice
Primary Production
Fisheries

Sea Ice

Migrating whales come to the Arctic to feed on nutritious prey (primary production), so a warmer climate may lead to increased migration. Tourism (boat tours, expedition, conventional cruise tourism) may disturb whales, but increasing tourism interest may also help to push through hunting bans (as in the Nuuk fjord).

POLAR BEARS

Isfjorden

Population

↗3K

Highlights

Population remains stable even though sea ice is melting

Challenges

Natural distribution range is changing dramatically

Tourism

Impact at sea: medium
Impact on land: medium
Value: high

Top 3 influences
Sea Ice
Seawater Temperature
Governance

Growing conflict between different area and resource usage (e.g. commercial fisheries, leisure fisheries, tourism, research, nature protection, resources extraction, military activities) is foreseen. Traditional governance schemes might struggle to address these issues due to diverging interests between governments and local stakeholders.

SEAWEED

(MACROALGAE)

- Isfjorden
- Porsangerfjorden
- Qeqertarsuup Tunua
- Nuup Kangerlua

Population

Highlights

Density & diversity increasing throughout the Arctic

Challenges

New species fundamentally altering ecosystems

Tourism

Impact at sea: low
Impact on land: low
Value: low

Top 3 influences
Seawater Temperature
Sea Ice
Light

Seaweed communities in Svalbard will transform into communities with species diversity and biomass similar to Northern Norwegian fjords over time.

Expert feedback on fisheries in the Arctic

SEAWEED

(MACROALGAE)

- Isfjorden
- Porsangerfjorden
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- Nuup Kangerlua

Harvest Trends

Local interest in fishery

New regulations would affect recreational fishery

Effects of

Atlantification: positive
Retreating glacier mixed
Melting sea ice: positive

Top 3 influences
Seawater Temperature
Sea Ice
Light

Ice-free coasts with low human impact may provide an opportunity for seaweed aquaculture and production of healthy food alternatives. This may become more important the more polluted southern sites become.

COD

- Isfjorden
- Porsangerfjorden

Catch Trends

Local interest in fishery

New regulations would affect recreational fishery

Effects of

- Atlantification: positive
- Retreating glacier: neutral
- Melting sea ice: positive

Top 3 influences
Seawater Temperature
Fisheries
Sea Ice

As temperatures increase and sea ice retreats, Arctic sites will become more and more similar to North Atlantic sites (i.e. Faroe Islands, Iceland), with all implications to biodiversity, fisheries, and livelihoods.

SHRIMP

 Isfjorden

 Porsangerfjorden

Catch Trends

Local interest in fishery

New regulations would affect recreational fishery

Effects of

- Atlantification: positive
- Retreating glacier: neutral
- Melting sea ice: positive

Top 3 influences
 Fisheries
 Sea Ice
 Seawater Temperature

Shrimp trawling is following the melting sea ice edge to the West and North of Svalbard and will require new regulations.

FLATFISH

(FLOUNDER + HALIBUT)

 Isfjorden

 Porsangerfjorden

Catch Trends

Local interest in fishery

New regulations would affect recreational fishery

Effects of

Atlantification: neutral
Retreating glacier: neutral
Melting sea ice: neutral

Top 3 influences
Fisheries
Seawater Temperature
Nutrients

Seawater Temperature

Without landing facilities in Svalbard, all catches must be landed further to the South.

POLLOCK

 Isfjorden

 Porsangerfjorden

Catch Trends

Local interest in fishery

New regulations would affect recreational fishery

Effects of

Atlantification: positive
Retreating glacier: neutral
Melting sea ice: neutral

Top 3 influences
Fisheries
Seawater Temperature
Sea ice

As sea ice retreats, fisheries that have historically been exploited in the southern Barents Sea will move North.

PINK SALMON

🎯 Isfjorden

🐟 Porsangerfjorden

Catch Trends

Local interest in fishery

New regulations would affect recreational fishery

Effects of

- Atlantification: positive
- Retreating glacier: neutral
- Melting sea ice: positive

Top 3 influences

- Sea Ice
- Primary Production
- Fisheries

Sea Ice

There is no fishery for the invasive pink salmon in the Norwegian High Arctic, but sports catches are increasing. With reports of catches now also coming from Isfjorden.

KING CRAB

 Isfjorden

 Porsangerfjorden

Catch Trends

Local interest in fishery

New regulations would affect recreational fishery

Effects of

Atlantification: positive
Retreating glacier: neutral
Melting sea ice: neutral

Top 3 influences Fisheries

The King Crab, an invasive species, has expanded along the Norwegian coast and is now pushing North into the Barents Sea. It tends to restructure any ecosystem it enters due to a lack of natural predators and a voracious appetite.

SNOW CRAB

 Isfjorden

 Porsangerfjorden

Catch Trends

Local interest in fishery

New regulations would affect recreational fishery

Effects of

Atlantification: neutral
Retreating glacier: neutral
Melting sea ice: neutral

Top 3 influences
Fisheries
Seawater Temperature

Seawater Temperature

Snow crabs, a commercially attractive species, have entered the Arctic region of the Barents Sea. Caught for the first time in Isfjorden in 2022-2023 (broadcast on Isfjord radio as tourism gimmick).

CATFISH

(WOLFFISH)

 Porsangerfjorden

Catch Trends

Local interest in fishery

New regulations would affect recreational fishery

Effects of

Atlantification: neutral
Retreating glacier: neutral
Melting sea ice: neutral

Top 3 influences Fisheries

Populations of sea urchins are increasing rapidly throughout the Arctic, with the appearance of sea urchin barrens now in Norway. What will this future bring for Arctic kelp forest ecosystems? Will it benefit or harm the natural predators of sea urchins, such as the catfish (wolffish).

SEAL

 Isfjorden

 Porsangerfjorden

Catch Trends

Local interest in fishery

New regulations would affect recreational fishery

Effects of

- Atlantification: negative
- Retreating glacier: negative
- Melting sea ice: negative

Top 3 influences
Sea Ice
Seawater Temperature

Commercial harvests in the Arctic are restricted to harp seals, which are severely impacted by melting sea ice. The ringed seal sport harvests in Svalbard remain stable.

Expert feedback on environment in the Arctic

SEA ICE

- 🌀 Isfjorden
- ⊗ Porsangerfjorden
- 🌀 Qeqertarsuup Tunua
- 🌀 Nuup Kangerlua

Trends

Why

Sea ice reflects sunlight, helping to keep the Arctic cool. Therefore, as more sea ice melts due to warmer waters, the warming feeds back on itself.

Top 3 influences

Seawater Temperature

Seawater Temperature

Tourism

Impact at sea: low
 Impact on land: low
 Value: high

Less ice is perceived by many (cruise) tourism operators as an enabler for more extensive & intensive tourism development. It will mean longer seasons, as well as going further into fjords and along coasts.

NB - Sea ice stopped forming consistently in Porsangerfjorden since 2011

GLACIERS

- Isfjorden
- Porsangerfjorden
- Qeqertarsuup Tunua
- Nuup Kangerlua

Trends

Why

When an Arctic fjord glacier melts so much that its leading edge no longer reaches the water, it goes from “marine-terminating” to “land-terminating”, which can completely disrupt the local marine ecosystem.

Top 3 influences
 Seawater Temperature
 Sea Ice
 Terrestrial Runoff

In Ilulisaat, Greenland, as glaciers melt and calve more frequently, it will create more ice bergs in the fjord and hence produce a more dramatic experience for tourists.

Tourism

Impact at sea: low
 Impact on land: low
 Value: high

POLLUTION

- Isfjorden
- Porsangerfjorden
- Qeqertarsuup Tunua
- Nuup Kangerlua

Trends

Why

Generally the Arctic is sparsely populated, so any increase to human presence, and the pollution that naturally follows, is acutely perceived.

Top 3 influences

- Tourism
- Fisheries
- Terrestrial Runoff

Terrestrial Runoff

As tourism on land and sea grow, so too follows the wake of pollution. This is seen as a real "detractor" for the industry and is a motivator for dealing with waste, beach cleaning, water treatment, etc.

Tourism

Impact at sea: high
Impact on land: high
Value: negative

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